

STATE OF HORSE FARMING IN UZBEKISTAN.

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Abstract: This article discusses the significance of horse breeding in the national economy, its current state, development prospects, and the number of horses in our country. Furthermore, the work to be carried out to increase production in horse breeding was analyzed, and relevant conclusions and recommendations were provided.

Keywords: Livestock, horse breeding, horse population, food products, productivity, efficiency, raw materials, meat, milk.

Introduction.

Horse breeding is considered one of the main branches of animal husbandry, and human society has been effectively using horses since ancient times, primarily as a means of transport, in military campaigns, as draft animals, and for product production. Currently, horse breeding in Uzbekistan is developing in close connection with agriculture, the economy, sports, tourism, and the food industry. The diversity of the country's natural and climatic conditions, the availability of vast pasture areas, and the practical implementation of modern breeding methods and scientific developments in breeding create favorable conditions for the development of horse breeding.

Especially in recent years, the decisions and decrees adopted by the government serve as an important factor in the modern development of the horse breeding industry, in particular, national and classical types of equestrian sports, ecotourism and horse travel, as well as in increasing the economic efficiency of the industry. The consistent continuation of these reforms will make it possible in the future to transform horse breeding into one of the most competitive and promising sectors of the country's livestock industry.

The economic significance of horse breeding in the republic is increasing year by year. Currently, horses are used not only in classical and national equestrian games but also in the production of meat and dairy products. In particular, the demand for kumis made from mare's milk is growing.

In the future, for the development of horse breeding in Uzbekistan, it is primarily important to improve the scientifically grounded breeding system, preserve the gene pool of the

Karabair breed, increase fodder crop areas, properly organize the veterinary service, and strengthen the fodder base. Also, increasing the number of existing horses, developing equestrian sports, introducing international experience in the field, and increasing the production of export-oriented horse products will serve to increase the economic efficiency of the industry.

Analysis of the horse population is of great importance for the effective development of horse breeding; it is an important factor in the proper organization of breeding work, the preservation of the gene pool of local breeds, the determination of fodder needs, the effective establishment of production, scientific management of the industry, and ensuring its sustainable development.

In recent years, a steady increase in the horse population has been observed in our country.

According to the National Statistics Committee, as of January 1, 2026, the total number of horses in all categories of farms in the republic amounted to 282,793 heads. This indicator shows an increase of 2.5% compared to the corresponding period of 2025.

When analyzed by region (according to Table 1), the Tashkent region holds the leading position in the number of horses. There are 56,969 horses in this province, accounting for 20.1% of the total number of horses in the country. It can be observed that there are 38,412 horses in the Kashkadarya region, 30,789 in the Samarkand region, 30,466 in the Jizzakh region, 28,096 in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, and 23,158 in the Navoi region.

Analysis shows that the number of horses is higher in regions where grazing livestock farming is developed. In the Tashkent, Kashkadarya, Samarkand, and Jizzakh regions, horses are widely used in sports, kokpar, breeding, and tourism. The popularity of kokpar games in these regions also has a positive impact on the development of horse breeding.

Relatively low indicators are observed in Andijan, Namangan, and Khorezm regions. Of we analyze the example of the Navoi region, in 2011 the number of horses in the region was 14,682 heads, in 2015 - 15,390 heads, in 2020 - 18,778 heads, and by the end of 2025 - 23,158 heads. We can observe that the growth of the horse population in 2025 compared to 2020 increased by 18.9%, compared to 2015 by 33.5%, and compared to 2011 by 36.6%

Table 1.

Information on the number of horses in Uzbekistan.

Regions	By year														
	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Republic of Uzbekistan	187445	195192	202212	208826	213407	216884	221410	230593	242470	247071	253625	260393	269002	275900	282793
Karakalpakstan	18529	18959	19559	20122	20274	20603	20473	22052	23809	24476	25918	26714	27610	28034	28096
Andijan region	6188	6459	6497	6484	6486	6422	6442	6438	6566	6694	6782	7099	7218	7401	7557
Bukhara region	4151	4347	4396	4421	4502	4523	4546	4867	5280	5653	6045	6796	7234	7923	8836
Jizzakh region	19162	19935	20749	21480	21740	22041	22331	24412	26602	27305	27898	27976	28996	29717	30466
Kashkadarya region	23116	24077	25187	26594	27275	27969	29288	30051	32019	32569	33274	33983	35478	36985	38412
Navoi region	14682	14994	15037	15283	15390	15600	15452	16612	17479	18778	19843	21199	21537	22223	23158
Namangan region	6324	6373	6429	6467	6521	6595	6655	6672	6468	6548	6572	6692	7003	7203	7378
Samarkand region	19726	20972	22113	22674	23131	23301	23531	23869	25946	26553	27273	27840	28737	29884	30789
Surkhandarya region	14861	15025	14923	14754	14841	14829	14936	14632	14166	14363	14753	15452	16180	16588	16879
Syrdarya region	9215	10287	10892	11706	12634	13633	15089	15399	15086	14433	14484	15206	16222	16808	17333
Tashkent region	40244	41989	43784	45690	46858	47488	48598	51318	54194	54805	55330	55612	56291	56494	56969
Fergana Region	6299	6824	7401	7891	8464	8553	8741	8842	9041	9063	9549	9801	10255	10504	10942
Khorezm region	4948	4951	5245	5260	5291	5327	5328	5429	5559	5604	5676	5728	5812	5859	5698
Tashkent city	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	255	227	228	295	429	277	280

Chart 1

Information on the number of horses (by regions as of January 1, 2026)

Chart 2

Change in the number of horses in the Navoi region (head).

In the republic, as of January 1, 2026, the total number of horses (282793) increased by 33.7% compared to the 2011 figure (187445).

In general, the fact that the number of horses in Uzbekistan is increasing from year to year shows that horse breeding is a promising and economically important industry. In particular, the development of national equestrian games and equestrian tourism is expected to further strengthen the future potential of this industry.

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